

The Influence of Product Placement and Product Attributes toward Purchase Intention of Subway Sandwich

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Abstract

In a world full of advertising clutter, we hardly ever pay attention to them. As more consumers avoid ads, brands strive to create ways for consumers to be exposed to their products and brands. The study aims to improve our knowledge of the variables that influence consumer purchase intention of the brands featured in Korean dramas. Product placement is effective advertising, but studies found that consumers will search for more information about the product feature they are interested in before purchasing. In particular, this research determines the influence of product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification, especially on food purchase intention in Indonesia. A total of 252 respondents who have watched Subway Sandwich featured in a Korean drama that is analyzed using multiple regression tests. This research utilizes convenience sampling by distributing an online questionnaire. Regression analysis shows that product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification simultaneously influence consumers' purchase intention. Unexpectedly, perceived price partially does not influence consumers' purchase intention on Subway Sandwich food. Our findings suggest a combining method both quantitative and qualitative, to gain better insight and identify additional factors that are not included in this research.

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Introduction

Consumers are currently bombarded with an abundance of advertising messages, but they hardly ever pay attention to them (D'Astous & Chartier, 2000). In a world full of advertising clutter, consumers complain tired of too many ads bringing a negative image of advertising (Mackay et al., 2009). With the emergence of new technologies that enable consumers to skip, mute, and avoid advertisements, traditional advertising has never been less effective (Cheon et al., 2016). Brands strive to create a variety of ways for consumers to be exposed to their products and brands (Smit et al., 2009). One of the ways is product placement, the integration of commercial content into noncommercial settings, i.e., a product plug generated through the combination of advertising and entertainment (Karrh, 1998; Russell & Belch, 2005; Schneider & Cornwell, 2005). Their target consumers might pay attention to product placements in television shows, movies, sports events, and other entertainment programs (I. Kim & Kim, 2004). Yet, no company has worked bolder than Subway, which has been in every Korean drama. Subway did not provide a list of how many Korean dramas in which Subway had appeared, but The New York Times (2021) found 17 appearances such as *Descendant of the Sun*, *The K2*, and *Goblin*, and the list is still going. The commercial success of products and brands placed in popular programs demonstrates the effectiveness of product placements in drama (Tian, 2014). Berkman (2021) stated that according to Colin Clark, the country director for Subway in Korea, which mentioned that "doing product placements in some popular dramas like "Descendants of the Sun" had a beneficial impact on global sales, particularly market in China, Taiwan, and Singapore". Prior studies found that product placements are significantly effective, but the findings state some limitations. Cheon et al. (2016) stated that their findings did not factor in consumers' level of need for the product. Furthermore, Karrh et al. (2003) added that the most common methods of evaluating placements are unaided recall and brand recognition, although the tracking of future related sales or measuring trade or general press coverage is becoming more prevalent. Additionally, most respondents Kit & P'ng (2014a) say that they will search for more information about the placed product feature they are interested in, such as size, color, quality, and product attributes/features before purchasing. When people begin looking for information about a certain product or service, they demonstrate their interest in it. This is aligned with the theory of purchase intention, according to (Natalia et al., 2021; S. Yu & Lee, 2019) purchase intentions can emerge after consumers are influenced by the product's quality and exciting information. Since, a customer purchase intention is the possibility of a consumer considering purchasing a certain brand, customers who are more likely to agree with the brand and find its product appealing will be more likely to purchase the product (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2004). Purchase intention is a key indicator for predicting consumption behavior (Keller, 2001). To comprehend consumer purchasing intention, marketers must first comprehend the consumption process and the utility of products in consumers' perceptions.

Jay Tansil et al. (2014) found that perceived price positively and significantly affects purchase intentions. Consumers are price sensitive, but their consumption is not always driven solely by price factors, particularly in food consumption (Hendriyanto & Soesanto, 2017). As per Ambolau et al. (2015), the brand image provides value and creates a halo effect for the entire product line of a company. A product with a pleasant image has a significantly better chance of being purchased than an awful one. When determining purchase intention, product quality is a crucial consideration. People use perceived quality to determine whether a product or service meets their expectations (Severt et al., 2022). Therefore, understanding the connection between food quality perception and customer behavior is critical for producers to remain market competitive. Since Indonesia is a country with a majority Muslim population, there might be another factor that can influence consumers to purchase, especially food. According

to the data from Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS), Indonesian Central Bureau of Statistics, the Muslim population in 2010 amounted to approximately 207,176,162 people, accounting for 87.18% of the total population in Indonesia, this makes Indonesia the number one country with the most populated by Muslims (Riaz & Chaudry, 2003). Therefore, Indonesian consumers must be more thorough in ensuring halal certification. As well as Subway Indonesia followed which has been halal-certified since day one of its opening last year (Subway Indonesia, 2022). According to Aisyah et al. (2019), Indonesian consumers are becoming more conscious of halal-certified foods. This finding is supported by (Awan et al., 2015; Aziz & Chok, 2013; Fitria et al., 2019), who found that halal certification and marketing significantly influence consumers' intention to purchase halal foods in Indonesia. The current research aims to explore whether the congruence between products placed and stories of drama and actor characteristics influence consumer purchase intentions toward Korean dramas and the placed brand under Indonesian characteristics. This study aims to improve on several variables that might influence consumer purchase intention of the brand feature in Korean dramas. The limitation of prior studies stated above acquiring more factors for consumers to purchase a product (Cheon et al., 2016; Karrh et al., 2003; Kit & P'ng, 2014a). Based on the explanation above, this study sets out to determine "The Influence of Product Placement, Perceived Price, Brand Image, Perceived Product Quality, and Halal Certification toward Purchase Intention among Indonesian Consumer Study on Subway Sandwich".

Literature Review

Purchase Intention

According to Kotler & Armstrong (2010), it is a condition or circumstance in which consumers are more likely to purchase a specific type of service or product. Purchase intention is defined as the desire to buy a specific brand (Shahbaz et al., 2009). According to (Natalia et al., 2021; S. Yu & Lee, 2019) purchase intentions can emerge after consumers are influenced by the product's quality and exciting information. According to (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2014) the indicators of an intention to buy include interest in seeking information about related products, considering making purchases, having an interest in trying, wanting to know products, and having the desire to own a product. From these statements, we can formulate the hypotheses as follows:

Product Placement

Product placement is an integration of commercial content into noncommercial settings, i.e., a product plug generated through the combination of advertising and entertainment (Karrh et al., 2003; Kit & P'ng, 2014a; Lehu, 2009; Russell & Belch, 2005; Schneider & Cornwell, 2005). (Hudson & Hudson, 2006) refers to a more advanced form of product placement in which a brand is integrated into a storyline in an entertainment context. According to Cheon et al. (2016) the following are product placement indicators: story-product congruence, perceived similarity, perceived likability, attitudes toward the drama, and attitudes toward the brand. Essentially, product placements that are well integrated into films have the potential to increase brand awareness and positive responses, especially when a celebrity is associated with it (Kumar, 2017). Aside from celebrities, the use of visual product placements may have contributed to the positive response. Because these types of placements are frequently more noticeable when watching films or dramas, they help keep the product or brand in the consumer's mind (Laban et al., 2020). Consumers intend to buy brands they are familiar with, but most likely brands they are very familiar with (Shahid et al., 2017). Pancaningrum & Ulani (2020), Kakkar & Nayak (2019), and L. Yu (2016) exposing consumers to product placement in films can have a significant impact on their purchase intention, particularly if their brand awareness, attitude, and recall are positive toward the brand featured in the film. Gageler et al.

(2016) contended that product placement has a positive correlation with purchase intention and that it has a positive influence on product placement, which increases their positive purchase intention, especially when it is with a favorite celebrity, despite their perception of it being unethical. Luo & Zhong (2015) the neutral attitude of most respondents toward placement marketing, which was regarded as an enterprise promotion tactic, and the higher purchase intention of more than 16% of respondents after watching movies, where the number was higher than those regarding placed brands and products as favorable (Filiery & McLeay, 2014). According to Belch & Belch, (2021); Candi et al., (2022) fluent placement marketing and significant introduction could more easily form positive attitudes of consumers toward brands and products to induce purchase intention. The result found product placement can influence purchase intention in a positive direction. Thus, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₁: Product placement influences purchase intention.

Perceived Price

Some products or services are purchased based on the customer's perceived price rather than the actual monetary price (Satriawan, 2020). Price perception is defined (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2015) as the customer's perception of the value received from the purchase. Price perception, according to (Lee et al., 2011), is an assessment made by consumers and the emotional form associated with whether the price offered by the seller and the price compared to other parties is reasonably acceptable or justifiable. Moreover, according to Stanton (2009), perceived prices are made up of several sub-variables, including affordability of prices, price competitiveness, price conformity with product quality, and price conformity with product benefits. Basically, in the condition of cognitive price information processing, consumers can make a comparison between the price determined and a price range that has formed in their minds for the product (Peter & Olson, 2010). But even for the same product, they hold different presumptions about it. It depends on the circumstances and challenges faced by consumers (Familmaleki et al., 2015). Each individual's assessment of whether a product's price is ordinary, cheap, or expensive differs (Peter & Olson, 2010). That is why price perception is one of the reasons why someone intends to buy. According to studies, price is the most important factor in determining brand loyalty and influences consumer purchase intention (Rai & Gupta, 2019). In his study, Langling Manorek (2016) investigates the impact of brand image, advertising, and perceived price on purchase intentions. His findings show that price perception positively and significantly affects purchase intentions. Jay Tansil et al. (2014) conducted a study that found that the perceived price of Cupcakes has a positive and significant effect on purchase intentions. Based on the findings above, we can conclude that perceive price has a significant impact on consumer purchase intentions. Thus, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₂: The perceived price influence purchase intention.

Brand Image

According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012) brand image is a collection of beliefs, ideas, and the impression held by someone about a product. As per (Ambolau et al., 2015), corporate image not only provides value but also creates a halo effect for the entire product line of a company. (Anselmsson et al., 2014) defined brand image as the customer's associations and beliefs regarding the brand. In essence, when a brand has a powerful image and favorable picture in the consumer's mind, the brand will always be remembered and the consumer's likelihood of purchasing a brand that is associated with is quite high. According to Keller (2012), the following are brand image indicators: the strength of brand association, the favorability of brand association, and the uniqueness of brand association. In essence, when a brand has a powerful image and favorable picture in the consumer's mind, the brand will always be

remembered and the consumer's likelihood of purchasing a brand that is associated with is quite high. A product with a pleasant image has a significantly better chance of being purchased than an awful one. As a result, consumer attitudes and actions toward a brand are heavily influenced by the brand's image (Kotler & Keller, 2012). Brand image is a critical factor in purchase intention (Esch et al., 2006). When the strategy causes consumers to speculate about the promoted product and decreases their purchase intention, the product's brand image suffers (Ho et al., n.d.). Wardani et al. (2020) proved that brand image significantly influences the consumer purchase intention of halal skin care. Ayub & Kusumadewi (2021) found aligned results that brand image has a significant positive effect on the purchase intention of an automotive product. Based on the findings above, we can conclude that brand image significantly impacts consumer purchase intentions. Thus, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₃: Brand image influences purchase intention.

Perceived Product Quality

People use perceived quality to determine whether a product or service meets their expectations (Severt et al., 2022). The perceived quality of a product is a subjective concept that consumers hold (Calvo-Porrall & Lévy-Mangin, 2017). Consumers evaluate the quality of any product based on its superiority and as a better alternative to any other available product or service (Keller, 2008). According to (Anselmsson et al., 2017), the indicator of perceived product quality is: (1) there is a high likelihood that merchandise bought at this store will be of extremely high quality (2) overall, this store sells high-quality merchandise (3) when shopping at this store, I expect to see the high quality. Since consumers always compare the product's quality to other available alternatives, quality perception varies depending on several factors. Thus, including the time of purchase or consumption of a product, as well as the location where it is purchased or consumed. Such as non-local products will be preferred by developing-country consumers because they are generally regarded as of high quality (Khattak & Shah, 2011), including food. To briefly summarize, perceived quality adds value to consumers by giving them a reason to buy and distinguishing the brand from competitors. Jay Tansil et al. (2014) discovered that perceived quality positively and significantly affected purchase intention at the SHMILY Cupcake shop in Manado. Gama et al., 2018) discovered that perceived quality had a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, which is consistent with the findings of Asma Saleem et al. (2015) and Kouce Lomboan (2017), who also found that perceived quality had a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Based on these studies, we can conclude that product quality influences consumer purchase intentions. Thus, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₄: Perceived product quality influences purchase intention.

Halal Certification

Halal food certification involves the examination of food processes such as preparation, slaughtering, cleaning, processing, handling, disinfecting, storing transportation, and management (Ratanamaneichat & Rakkarn, 2013). According to (Awan et al., 2015), brands that invest in raising customer awareness of halal food will boost the company's marketing program while also influencing customer confidence in eating halal food. The Halal label or certification has effectively attracted consumers' intentions to purchase halal food (Awan et al., 2015). However, this does not preclude it from applying to non-Muslim consumers because, in today's society, halal certification is regarded as an assurance of a high-quality product that adheres to good manufacturing practices (GMP) (Rosnan et al., 2015). According to (Muslichah & Ibrahim, 2021), the indicator of halal certifications is: (1) A halal logo is important in choosing a product (2) Choose the product based on the halal logo (3) Be careful in choosing

foods that have a halal logo (4) The use of Halal Certification and logos ensures that the food is Halal (5) When buying a product, the food has to be halal certified (6) Halal certification increases the market capacity of the product (7) The Halal logo has a higher appeal than products that do not have a halal logo. The indicators on 'Halal certification increases the market capacity of the product' is eliminated because they are not under this research. Primarily, halal certification is important for providing assurance, particularly for Muslim consumers. However, this does not preclude it from applying to non-Muslim consumers because, in today's society, halal certification is regarded as an assurance of a high-quality product that adheres to good manufacturing practices (GMP) (Rosnan et al., 2015). In a Muslim-majority country like Indonesia, halal certification is critical when selling food. Today's Muslim consumers face a plethora of product options that may or may not be halal, so marketers use halal certification on their products to indirectly convince target consumers that their products are sharia-compliant (Muslichah et al., 2014). Halal labeling or certification has been shown to effectively attract consumers' intent to purchase food (Awan et al., 2015), halal fast food (Fitria et al. (2019), not only for Muslims but also for non-Muslim consumers (Aziz & Chok, 2013). The result found that halal certification can influence purchase intention in a positive direction. Thus, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H₅: Halal certification influences purchase intention.

Additionally, the five hypotheses above predict that product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification affect purchase intention. Consequently, the sixth hypothesis predicts the simultaneous effects of all variables on purchase intentions. Hence, the sixth hypothesis is:

H₆: Product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification influence purchase intention.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: (Cheon et al., 2016) & Modified by Researcher (2022)

Methodology

Type of Research

This study used a quantitative approach to gather information on the relationship among variables. The primary data for this study is mainly taken in October 2022 through an online questionnaire, obtained through Google Forms. The first section accumulated the demographic of respondents in terms of gender, age, city of domicile, educational background, and monthly expenses (IDR). The second section for the filter questions, known as contingency questions, is

used in this study to assess highly targeted surveys. Several questions are extended to filter people familiar with Subway Sandwich and have watched Korean Dramas with Subway Sandwich in its scenes. The third section assessed product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, halal certification, and purchase intention which consists of 37 questions. Respondents will select a number between 1 and 5 based on the statements from (1-Strongly disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Somewhat agree, 4-Agree, 5-Strongly agree). These are acceptable levels of intensity that can be modified and used in statistical analysis (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). To ensure that respondents fully understood the questions, the survey was translated both into Indonesian and English. Before moving on to the main test, validity and reliability tests were conducted.

Sample and data collection

The population in this study is men and women who live in Indonesia and have ever watched Korean Dramas with Subway Sandwich in their scenes. This study is conducted using a non-probability convenience sampling method. However, because the samples were chosen at random, bias and outside influences may arise (Saunders et al., 2009). Roscoe (1975) in (Sugiyono, 2017) states that a sample size of more than 30 people and less than 500 is suitable for the majority of studies when determining the appropriate number of samples. The researcher has received 513 responses, but there are so many biased responses (non-random deviation) to resolve this problem, some elimination of data has been conducted. The sample size will therefore be 252 respondents after the elimination.

Data analysis and result

Validity and reliability test

The first step involved a validity test to determine the extent to which the questions contained in the questionnaire items can define a variable. The validity test has been examined between the correlation of the questions and the total score which resulted in the r_{table} value of 0.123. The variables of product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, halal certification, and purchase intention were declared valid and passed the test. This is because the value in the r_{count} column is greater than the value in the r_{table} (0.123) for each question variable item. The reliability test has been conducted through SPSS before continuing to further analysis. The reliability coefficient, or Cronbach's alpha value, shows how strongly items in a set are positively correlated (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). The reliability test resulted in Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.883 which is >0.6 , indicating that all variables with a total of 37 questions are reliable.

Classical Assumption

This study also conducted several classical assumption tests, including normality, heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity tests. Firstly, a normality test was applied to the research model. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistical test is used in this study to determine whether the data is normally distributed or not. The data is considered normal if sig. (2-tailed) is more than 0.05 ($p - value > 0.05$) (Ghozali, 2016; Malhotra, 2019). Therefore, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test result in this study was $0.200 > 0.05$, demonstrating a normally distributed set of data. Secondly, to assess the data's heteroscedasticity, the Glejser method is used. It calculates the significance of the independent variable using the absolute residual from the data derived from the independent variables. The significance value for the heteroscedasticity test must be greater than 0.05. It can be comprehended that the sig value of product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived quality, and halal certification are 0.067, 0.184, 0.103, 0.331, and 0.110 respectively. This indicates that none of the five regressions' variance residuals are heteroscedastic. The last test for the classical assumption is

the multicollinearity test. This method is to test the variance inflation factors. The decision rule for multicollinearity is that the VIF value must be less than 10 and the tolerance level is greater than 0.1 (Miles, 2014). The results were less than 10, ranging from 1.042 (the minimum) to 2.630 (the maximum). The result of tolerance for product placement is 0.661, the perceived price is 0.380, the brand image is 0.479, for perceived quality is 0.960, and halal certification is 0.738. The result of all the tolerance values obtained is > 0.1 , showing that multicollinearity was not an issue in this study.

Demographic

Table 1 displays data from 252 respondents that knew about Subway Sandwich and have watched Subway Sandwich product placement in Korean drama. Below is some information about the characteristics of the respondents to this study, regarding gender, age, domicile city, educational background, and average expenses per month.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis of Sample

	Items	Number of Respondents	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	8	3.2
	Female	241	95.6
	Prefer not to say	3	1.2
Age	Under 20 years old	22	8.7
	20-25 years old	107	42.5
	26-30 years old	63	25.0
	30+ years old	60	23.8
Domicile City	Jakarta	35	13.9
	Surabaya	46	18.3
	Other	171	67.9
Educational Background	SMA/High School	81	32.1
	D3/Diploma	20	7.9
	S1/Bachelor Degree	127	50.4
	S2/Master Degree	15	6.0
	Other	9	3.6
Expenses (avg. per month)	< IDR 1.000.000	60	23.8
	IDR 1.000.000 - IDR 2.000.000	70	27.8
	IDR 2.100.000 - IDR 3.000.000	40	15.9
	IDR 3.100.000 - IDR 4.000.000	22	8.7
	> IDR 4.000.000	60	23.8

Source: Primary data collected by researcher, 2022

Hypothesis Analysis

T-Test (Partial) Analysis

Table 2 Result of T-Test Coefficient^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	R Square		
(Constant)	-4.756	2.078		-2.289	0.023
Product Placement	0.129	0.040	0.183	3.267	0.001
Perceived Price	0.083	0.090	0.055	0.922	0.358
Brand Image	0.368	0.095	0.302	3.855	0.000
Perceived Quality	0.407	0.118	0.241	3.451	0.001
Halal Certification	0.091	0.029	0.153	3.105	0.002

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Based on the T-Test result above, showing that the significance value for product placement (X_1) is $0.001 < 0.05$, then it can be concluded that product placement partially influences the purchase intention (Y). The significance value for the perceived price (X_2) is $0.038 > 0.05$, then it can be concluded that the hypotheses of the perceived price partially do not influence the purchase intention (Y). The significance value for brand image (X_3) is $0.000 < 0.05$, then it can

be concluded that the hypotheses of the brand image partially influence the purchase intention (Y). The significance value for perceived product quality (X_4) is $0.001 < 0.05$, then it can be concluded that the hypotheses of perceived product quality partially influence the purchase intention (Y). The significance value for halal certification (X_4) is $0.002 < 0.05$, then it can be concluded that the hypotheses of halal certification partially influence the purchase intention (Y).

F-Test (Simultaneous) Analysis

**Table 3 Result of F-Test
ANOVA^a**

Model	F	Sig.
Regression	36.804	.000 ^b
Residual		

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

The following can be used to test the hypothesis throughout the table above:

According to table 3, given that the significance value for the interaction between the product placement variable (X_1), perceived price (X_2), brand image (X_3), perceived quality (X_4), halal certification (X_5) on purchase intention (Y) is $0.000 > 0.05$, it can be said that the five variables simultaneously influenced purchase intention (Y).

**Table 4 Coefficient of Correlation & Determination
Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.654 ^a	0.428	0.416	3.003

- Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention
- Predictors: (Constant), Halal Certification, Perceived Quality, Product Placement, Perceived Price, Brand Image

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

According to table 4, the R Square value was 0.428, which indicates that 42.8% of purchase intention was affected by product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived quality, and halal certification variables. While the remaining 65.4% was influenced by other factors outside the scope of this study.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

According to **table 2**, the regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

$$= -4.756 + 0.129X_1 + 0.083X_2 + 0.368X_3 + 0.407X_4 + 0.091X_5 + e$$

The regression equation's findings and the multiple regression analysis' interpretations are as follows: The fact that constant (a) has a negative value, i.e., -4.756, indicates that if the product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived quality, and halal certification are all equal to zero (0), then their purchase intention has decreased. The findings demonstrated the value of product placement regression coefficient (0.129), perceived price (0.083), brand image (0.368), perceived quality (0.407), and halal certification (0.091), which indicates that all 5 variables positively influence purchase intention. Due to $0.407 > 0.129, 0.083, 0.368, \text{ and } 0.091$ then perceived product quality is a variable that has a dominant influence on purchase intention.

Descriptive Statistic Analysis

Table 5 Descriptive Statistic of Product Placement

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	X1.1	Subway Sandwich is part of the K-drama that I watch.	3.94	High
2.		K-drama describes Subway Sandwich as a cool restaurant.	3.89	High
3.		The scene with Subway Sandwich makes K-drama more interesting.	3.52	High
4.	X1.2	I feel that I have a similar lifestyle as the actor in the K-drama that I watch.	2.55	Low
5.		I can relate to the actor's condition in the K-drama.	3.67	High
6.		I seem to have a similar idea to the actor in the K-drama.	3.23	Medium
7.	X1.3	The actor in the K-drama has a good look.	4.70	Very High
8.		The actor makes the K-drama more interesting.	4.71	Very High
9.	X1.4	It is interesting to see the K-drama.	4.75	Very High
10.		I enjoy watching K-drama.	4.78	Very High
11.	X1.5	I am interested in The Subway Sandwich in the drama.	3.93	High
12.		I felt positive about The Subway Sandwich in K-drama.	3.83	High
13.		The Subway Sandwich in K-drama triggers my curiosity.	3.90	High
Total Mean			3.95	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Table 6 Descriptive Statistic of Perceived Price

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	X2.1	I can afford the Subway Sandwich.	3.86	High
2.	X2.2	I think Subway Sandwich is cheaper than the other similar brands.	2.82	Medium
3.	X2.3	I think Subway Sandwich's price is comparable to its quality	3.62	High
4.	X2.4	I think Subway Sandwich's price suits with the benefits I get.	3.34	Medium
Total Mean			3.41	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Table 7 Descriptive Statistic of Brand Image

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	X3.1	Subway Sandwich is popular as a fresh fast-food.	3.88	High
2.	X3.2	Subway Sandwich is the favorite brand of sandwich product.	3.49	High
3.	X3.3	Subway Sandwich has customizable menu.	3.93	High
4.		Subway logo gives the impression of freshness.	4.02	High
5.		Subway logo gives the impression of health.	3.85	High
Total Mean			3.83	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Table 8 Descriptive Statistic of Perceived Product Quality

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	X4.1	It is very likely that Subway Sandwich uses fresh ingredients.	4.10	High
2.		It is very likely that Subway Sandwich seems to use healthy ingredients.	4.01	High
3.	X4.2	Overall, I believe Subway Sandwich sells high-quality sandwiches.	4.04	High
4.	X4.3	Someday, when I eat at Subway Sandwich, I expect to see high quality sandwiches.	4.66	Very High
Total Mean			4.20	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Table 9 Descriptive Statistic of Halal Certification

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	X5.1	Halal logo is important for me in choosing food.	4.30	Very High
2.	X5.2	I will choose the food which has the halal logo.	4.26	Very High
3.	X5.3	I always make sure the foods that I consume have halal logo.	4.05	High
4.	X5.4	The halal logo convinces me that the food is Halal.	4.48	Very High
5.	X5.5	When I buy some food, I want the food to be halal certified.	4.13	High
6.	X5.6	The food with Halal logo is more appealing than the one without a halal logo.	3.91	High
Total Mean			4.19	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Table 10 Descriptive Statistic of Purchase Intention

No.	Indicator	Statement	Mean	Remark
1.	Y1	I am interested in searching for all information related to Subway Sandwich.	3.28	High
2.	Y2	If I want to buy sandwiches, I would consider buying Subway Sandwich.	3.78	High
3.	Y3	I am interested in trying Subway Sandwich.	4.21	Very High
4.	Y4	I want to know more about Subway Sandwich.	3.63	High
5.	Y5	I intend to purchase sandwich from Subway Sandwich someday.	4.29	Very High
Total Mean			3.84	High

Source: Primary data processed by researcher, 2022

Discussion

Partial Influence

The product placement variable's statistical analysis revealed that the regression coefficient was positive at 0.129. The product placement variable's T-test results show that the *p-value* is 0.001. The *p-value* is less than the significance level ($0.001 < 0.05$). According to the findings, product placement influences consumers' purchase intention on Subway Sandwich. This result is relevant to Candi et al. (2022) that fluent placement marketing and significant introduction could more easily form positive attitudes of consumers toward brands and products to induce purchase intention. Due to product placements, a product plug generated through the combination of advertising and entertainment, their target consumers might more pay attention to it. According to Laban et al. (2020), these types of placements are frequently more noticeable when watching films or dramas, they help keep the product or brand in the consumer's mind, especially when it is associated with a favorite celebrity (Gageler et al., 2016). This is reasonable because the use of visual product placements may have contributed to the positive response, consumers intend to buy brands that they are familiar with. As a result, there will be a positive response that the consumer's intention to purchase Subway Sandwich over competing ones. However, these findings are different from the results of recent research by Uribe (2016) which asserts that product placement did not affect purchase intentions. Notwithstanding, based on the data from the questionnaire asked on product placement indicator, the respondents generally agreed with the high average statement "I am interested in The Subway Sandwich in the drama", "I felt positive about The Subway Sandwich in K-drama", and "The Subway Sandwich in K-Drama triggers my curiosity", with each average value are 3.93, 3.83, and 3.90 (Table 5). Moreover, the statement "The actor in the K-drama has a good look", "The actor makes the K-drama more interesting", "It is interesting to see the K-drama", and "I enjoy watching K-drama", have very high averages around 4.70 - 4.78. Essentially, product placements that are well integrated into films have the potential to increase brand awareness and positive responses, especially when a celebrity is associated with it (Kumar, 2017).

The perceived price variable's statistical analysis revealed that the regression coefficient was positive at 0.083. The partial T-test results in table 6 demonstrated the perceived price did not influence consumers' intentions to buy Subway Sandwich. The hypothesis is unacceptable since the value of 0.922 $t_{\text{count}} < t_{\text{table}} 1,969$ or the significance value is $0.038 > 0.05$. Therefore, whether the perceived price is high or low will not influence consumers' purchasing intentions. This is against the findings of studies by Jay Tansil et al. (2014) that the perceived price of Cupcakes has a positive and significant effect on purchase intentions. On the contrary, given that prices are not always taken into account when consumers make purchase decisions, this result is pertinent to Schiffman et al. (2010) and Setiawan & Achyar (2012) hypotheses. This was demonstrated by the descriptive statistics table results for the variable perceived price, which shows a high level of perceived price with a value of 3.42. This suggests that when customers purchase Subway Sandwich, they do not think about the cost. Since Subway Sandwich already meets high-quality standards and is reasonably priced, consumers are less likely to consider the cost involved. These attitudes will be strengthened and the likelihood of making purchases with adjusted prices will increase. It can be described in the statement "I think Subway Sandwich's price is comparable to its quality", with a high average of 3.62. In addition, the respondents stated that they can afford the Subway Sandwich which has an average of 3.86 shown in table 6, they intentionally purchase the Subway Sandwich out of curiosity. The brand image variable's statistical analysis revealed that the regression coefficient was positive at 0.368. The partial T-test result demonstrated that brand image influences consumers' intention to purchase Subway Sandwich. H_{a3} is accepted as the value of 3.855 $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}} 1,969$ or the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$. This finding is aligned with Ayub & Kusumadewi (2021) that brand image has a significant positive effect on purchase intention. Nevertheless, this finding is contradictory to H. W. Kim et al. (2012) that brand image does not affect purchase intention. In essence, when a brand has a powerful image and favorable picture in the consumer's mind, the brand will always be remembered and the consumer's likelihood of purchasing that particular brand is quite high. The product with a pleasant image has a significantly better chance of being purchased than the one with an awful image. As a result, consumer attitudes and actions toward a brand are heavily influenced by the brand's image (Kotler & Keller, 2012). This finding paralleled all 5 statements in the brand image variable, with a quite high average result at 3.83. Considerably, Subway Sandwiches and its attributes have an image of a fresh, healthy, and customizable sandwich that encourages people to purchase it. The perceived product quality variable's statistical analysis revealed that the regression coefficient was positive at 0.407. The partial T-test result demonstrated that perceived product quality influences consumers' intention to purchase Subway Sandwich. H_{a4} is accepted as the value of 3.451 $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}} 1,969$ or the significance value is $0.001 < 0.05$. This result is consistent with the findings of Gama et al. (2018) and Kouce Lomboan (2017), that perceived quality had a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. People use perceived quality to determine whether a product or service meets their expectations or not (Severt et al., 2022). Since consumers always compare the product's quality to other available alternatives, quality perception varies depending on several factors. Thus, including the location where it is purchased or consumed. Such as foreign products like Subway Sandwiches will be preferred by developing-country consumers because they are generally regarded as of high quality. This aligned with the very high average of 4.66 results on the "Someday, when I eat at Subway Sandwich, I expect to see high-quality sandwiches" statement. This perceived quality adds value to consumers by giving them a reason to buy and distinguishing Subway Sandwich from its competitors. The halal certification variable's statistical analysis revealed that the regression coefficient was positive at 0.091. The partial T-test result demonstrated that halal certification influences consumers' intention to purchase Subway Sandwich. H_{a5} is accepted as the value of 3.105 $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}} 1,969$ or the significance value is $0.002 < 0.05$. This

finding is aligned as halal labeling or certification has been shown to effectively attract consumers' intent to purchase halal fast food by Fitria et al. (2019). This finding conflicts with Aspan et al. (2017), which claimed that the halal label has no impact on consumers' purchasing intentions. Since this study was conducted in Indonesia, which is a majority of Muslim population, halal certification is important for assuring their food. Furthermore, today's Muslim consumers face a plethora of product options that may or may not be halal, so marketers use halal certification on their products to indirectly convince target consumers that their products are sharia-compliant (Muslichah et al., 2014). Primarily, halal certification is important for providing assurance, particularly for Muslim consumers. However, this does not preclude it from applying to non-Muslim consumers because, in today's society, halal certification is regarded as an assurance of a high-quality product that adheres to good manufacturing practices (GMP) (Rosnan et al., 2015). The respondents generally agreed with the statement of "Halal logo is important for me in choosing food" with an average of 4.30 as considered very high. Also, a very high average result of 4.26 on the statement "I will choose the food which has the halal logo". Expectedly, the statement "The halal logo convinces me that the food is Halal" surpasses the average almost full-five scores at 4.48. Remarkably, the halal logo or certification in Subway Sandwich ensures consumers' purchase intention for Subway Sandwich foods.

Simultaneous Influence

The purpose of this study is to determine the simultaneous influence of product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification on purchase intention. According to the analysis above, the regression analysis shows an *R Square* of 0.428. This indicates that 42.8% of purchase intentions can be accounted for by product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification variable, while the remaining 65.4% is accounted for by factors that are not included in this research model. This finding also demonstrates that the 0.000 *p-value* is less than the 0.05 significance level. In conclusion, product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification all influence consumers' intention to purchase. This research accordance with (Kit & P'ng, 2014b; Muhamamd Badar, 2021; Nurcahyo & Hudrasyah, 2017; Rai & Gupta, 2019; Setiawan & Achyar, 2012) product placement, perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification simultaneously influence purchase intention.

Conclusion

Based on the research and analysis mentioned above, it can be concluded that product placement in Korean dramas, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification simultaneously influence the purchase intention of Subway Sandwich. However, the variable of perceived price partially does not influence the purchase intention of Subway Sandwich. The results of this research imply that: The more frequently Subway Sandwich appears in Korean dramas, the more it will encourage consumer's purchase intention. The more positive images of Subway Sandwich in consumer's minds, the stronger the perception of halal and quality of Subway sandwich products, as well as the stronger the Subway Sandwich brand image being embedded in consumers' minds, and the more it will encourage consumer's purchase intention. However, whether the perceived price is high or low will not alter consumers' purchase intention. Consumers are less likely to think about the associated costs and have a greater tendency to make purchases with adjusted prices.

Limitation

First of all, the time frame for the research is only a few weeks, which is very limited and prevents the researcher from conducting a thorough investigation of the subject. Furthermore,

because convenience sampling was used as a sampling technique, only a limited generalization can be made about the population as a whole. In the study, motivational bias was also discovered. The desire to support one's particular opinions, express a dissatisfying point of view or express interest in the research topic can all serve as motivation for participation. That is why the researcher has eliminated some responses.

Suggestions for Subway

Statement number 4 on the product placement variable has the lowest score, with 2.55 considered as a low average, which is "I feel that I have a similar lifestyle as the actor in the K-drama that I watch". After all, it refers to an expectation of the viewer's perceived similarity with the actor and generates positive attitudes toward the drama and the brands placed. The researcher suggests that Subway Sandwich should consider this matter. Subway Sandwich should try to make improvements to its product placement. The visual product placements on the scene should be having a similar lifestyle to their consumers, to encourage more positive responses to its product placement. Since the respondent who watches Subway Sandwich placement in Korean drama is 95.6% dominated by females, Subway Sandwich should consider what kind of occasion or event would happen to enjoy Subway Sandwich for female consumers. For example, it might be a scene pictured a group of females gossiping while eating Subway Sandwich, rather than having a work meeting there. It might be more appealing to female consumers because it is similar to their daily life. Statement number 2 on the perceived price variable has the lowest score, with 2.82 considered a medium average, which is "I think Subway Sandwich is cheaper than the other similar brands". The respondents agreed that Subway sandwiches are not cheaper than the competitors. However, the perceived price in this research does not influence the purchase intention of Subway Sandwich. Therefore, whether the perceived price is high or low will not influence consumers' purchasing intentions. In this research, the respondents were dominated by females, aged between 20-25 years old, and spent more than IDR 1.000.000 per month. This type of group might be from affluent families and their expenses might still depend on their parents. Thereupon, the prices given by Subway Sandwich are not taken into account when the respondents are going to purchase it. This is strengthened by the statement "I think Subway Sandwich's price is comparable to its quality", the respondents thought that the price of a Subway Sandwich is equal to its quality. Since the pricing strategy of Subway sandwich has complemented its target market, the researcher suggests that Subway should be able to maintain its quality and strengthen the efforts of conveying its value to the consumers and potential consumers. Hopefully, this research can be a reference for marketers who want to advertise through product placement in Korean drama or any other entertainment programs as a media that can influence purchasing intention. Product placement strategies in Korean dramas can promote and introduce their products widely, especially to the target market of young adult females. Before implementing a product placement strategy in a K-Drama, the Subway fast food restaurant chain or other businesses must take into account several factors:

1. The story-product congruence refers to integrating the placed product into the drama's storyline or plot.
2. Perceived similarity; refers to an expectation of the viewer's perceived similarity with the actor and generates positive attitudes toward the drama and the brands placed.
3. Perceived likability; refers to whether the character was personally likable or dislikable and how it influences the viewer's attitude toward the drama and brand placed.
4. Attitudes toward the drama; refer to how the product-story congruency facilitates viewers to favorable responses toward the drama.
5. Attitudes toward the brand; refer to how the product-story congruency facilitates viewers to favorable responses toward the brand placed.

Hence, a prior study found that product placements are significantly effective, but the findings state some limitations. Most respondents in Kit & P'ng, (2014a) research say that they will search for more information about the placed product feature they are interested in, such as size, color, quality, and product attributes/features before purchasing the information-seeking stage. Since people begin looking for information about a certain product or service, they demonstrate their interest in it. Fundamentally, that is why marketers should also pay more attention to other several factors especially for purchasing food in Indonesia. For example, this study also examined perceived price, brand image, perceived product quality, and halal certification variables that might influence purchase intentions of food among Indonesian consumers.

Suggestions for Future Study

The future researcher can assemble quantitative and qualitative methods, particularly to gain insight into each item that is related to the questionnaire statement to obtain a better explanation for each variable and, at the very least, to provide the applied implication more precisely. In this manner, it is possible to find out more particular deeper information, about how product placement affects consumers' intentions to make purchases. Future research is expected to identify additional factors that can influence customers' purchase intention since the result show that the remaining 65.4% is accounted for by factors that are not included in this research model.

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